

RESEARCH ON THE TECHNOLOGY OF YARN PRODUCTION FROM FIBERS RECOVERED FROM KNITTED FABRIC SCRAPS

Sh.M.Shodieva

Doctoral student, Master's student

U.M. Duysenbayeva

Prof.,

S.L.Matismailov

Prof.

Kholiyarov M.Sh.

Assoc.

Tashkent Institute of Textile and Light Industry

Tel: +998977177323

E-mail: sshaxzoda250@gmail.com

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Abstract. The article presents the results of experimental studies on obtaining regenerated fiber from knitted garment waste and producing yarn from it.

Аннотация. В статье приведены результаты экспериментальных исследований по получению восстановленного волокна из трикотажных швейных отходов и производству из них пряжи.

Keywords: fiber, secondary raw materials, regenerated fiber, scrap, polyester, cotton, tex, length, twist.

Ключевые слова: волокно, вторичное сырье, восстановленное волокно, обрез, полиэфир, хлопок, текс, длина, крутка.

Introduction.

In our republic, as a result of the annual increase in the volume of processing of local raw materials and the production of clothing, a large amount of textile secondary raw material resources is formed. In 2024, 540 thousand tons of knitted fabric were produced, of which 20% or 100 thousand tons are waste. In the world, technological waste and secondary raw material resources of the textile industry account for 25% of the total processed textile raw materials. This is a huge reserve, and the production of textile products from it is a pressing issue. The effective and rational use of secondary raw material resources has a direct impact on the development of the local textile industry.

Obtaining high-quality regenerated fiber from garment industry waste, including knitted fabric scraps, and producing yarn and non-woven fabrics from them is a pressing task in our republic [1-7].

Experimental studies. In this research work, experiments were conducted on obtaining regenerated fiber from garment knitwear scraps and spinning yarn

from them on a pneumomechanical spinning machine. Sewing scraps were first cut to a length of 40-60 cm on a QD 350 cutting machine installed at "EURASIA ALLIANCE TEX" LLC. The cut sewing scraps were placed on the lattice supply of the Chinese firm "Shandong Shunxing Machinery." Fragments of the same thickness on the feed grating were fed to the loosening drum, covered with the SMPL garnish, using feed raffle cylinders. Then, a layer of regenerated fibers was formed from the scraps in the condenser, samples were taken from the regenerated fibers, and the yield of the regenerated fibers was determined.

Based on the research plan, the results of the experiment on assessing the efficiency of the scrap loosening machine were analyzed. The operating efficiency of the improved pinching machine is presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Efficiency of fiber separation of knitted garments

№	Name of indicators	Fiber separation efficiency, %	
		Scrap	
		Enterprise	Experiment
1	Fragment length, mm	-	40-60
2	Fiber mass composition: - amount of recovered fibers, % - the number of unraveled threads, % - unworn pieces of scrap quantity, %	77,6 19,7 2,7	89,5 9,3 1,2

Analysis of the results of the conducted experiments showed that after passing the scraps through a pinching machine, the amount of restored fibers in the fiber mass in the experiment was 89.5%, the amount of unraveled yarn was 9.3%, and the amount of unraveled scraps was 1.2%.

One of the important properties of fibers obtained after separating scraps into fibers is the length of the restored fibers. To measure the length of the restored fibers with an error of 3%, the total number of fibers was taken as 500 pieces, the test results were processed according to the rules of mathematical statistics, and the distribution of fiber lengths in the samples was obtained.

Average indicators of the length of recovered fibers are presented in Table

Table 2

Average indicators of the length of recovered fibers

Restored fiber indicators	Restored fiber	
	Scrap	
	Enterprise	Enterprise
Staple length of fiber, mm	22,1	25,4
Fiber modal length, mm	16,9	19,3
Average fiber length, mm	17,5	25,4
Coefficient of variation by fiber length, %	44,8	38,8
Distribution of fiber by length, %		
7 – 15 mm	24,6	14,9
16 – 20 mm	21,3	26,9
21 – 25 mm	39,3	45,7
26 – 30 mm	13,6	10,4
31 – 35 mm	1,2	2,1

Analysis of the indicators of the nominal length distribution showed that 85% of fibers are suitable for spinning. It has been established that the presence of long fibers in the composition of regenerated fibers can serve as a basis for their use as fibrous raw materials.

Then, samples were taken from the regenerated fibers processed at the enterprise LLC "YEUROAZIA ALLIANCE TEX" and the experimental work was continued. The experiments were conducted under the production conditions of the enterprise LLC "UZYARN HOUSE TEXTILE." In the experiment, 50 kg of regenerated fibers and 5 kg of polyester fibers were taken from knitted scraps, mixed by the layer method, and the mixture was prepared manually. The production of yarn from a mixture of 90% regenerated fibers from knitted scraps and 10% regenerated fibers from polyester fiber was carried out on the following technological equipment of the enterprise LLC "UZYARN HOUSE TEXTILE." The restored fiber mixture was placed in the feed conveyor of the BO-E feeding-mixing machine. From it, the fiber mass was passed through the TO-T1 carding machine, the MX-U mixing machine, and the FD-S fiber mixing unit with air suction. On the TS-15 carding machine, equipped with an IDF-2 device, carded sliver with a linear density of 6.0 kteks was prepared. Linear density on the BD-480 Saurer Schlafhorst pneumomechanical spinning machine from carded sliver obtained from a carding machine OE yarn of 50 tex (Ne12) was produced and its physical

and mechanical properties were determined. Physical and mechanical indicators of yarn with a linear density of 50 tex (Ne12) Presented in Table 3.

The physical and mechanical indicators of the yarn were determined, and the obtained results were summarized in Table 3.

Table 3
Physico-mechanical indicators of threads

No	Restored fiber indicators	Enterprise	Enterprise
1	Linear density of yarn, tex	50	50
2	Coefficient of variation by linear density, %, CV	0,98	0,83
3	Breaking load, sN	573,5	641,5
4	Specific breaking load, Rkm, cN/tex	11,47	12,83
5	Coefficient of variation by specific breaking load, CV {Rkm}, %	8,30	8,28
6	Breaking work, N cm	8,04	9,76
7	Extension, %,	5,04	5,98
8	Coefficient of variation by length, %, CV	8,51	6,48
9	Thread unevenness in cross-section, %:		
	- linear, Um	10,64	9,47
	- quadratic, cm	13,49	12,09
10	Appearance defects: Including		
	-thinner areas (-50%), pcs/km	6	2
	-thickness (+50%), pcs/km	43,5	22,5
	-neps (+200%), pcs/km	249	334
	-neps (+280%), pcs/km	115	66
11	Twistedness, turns/m	650	650
12	Coefficient of variation by twist, %, CV	4,9	3,2

Analysis of the results. Analysis of the obtained results showed that the specific breaking load (Rkm) of yarns spun from regenerated fibers increased by 11.85%, the elongation at break by 18.65%, the coefficient of variation (CV) by Rkm decreased by 5.8%, the coefficient of variation by elongation by 23.85%, and the coefficient of variation by twist (CV) by 34.7%.

Conclusion. The results obtained in the experiment on the production of OE yarn with a linear density of 50 tex (Ne12) from a mixture consisting of 90% regenerated fibers and 10% polyester fiber from knitted scraps showed the possibility of increasing the volume of production. The yarn obtained in the experiment can be used in the production of weaving and knitwear for household and technical purposes.

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